

Immune-expression profile identification in a group of Proliferative Verrucous Leukoplakia patients: A pre-cancer niche for Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma development

Carlos Llorens¹, Beatriz Soriano¹, Lucia Trilla-Fuertes², Leticia Bagan³, Ricardo Ramos-Ruiz⁴, Angelo Gamez-Pozo^{2,5}, Cristina Peña^{6*}, and Jose V. Bagan^{3*}

¹Biotechvana, Parc Científic, Universitat de València, Paterna, Valencia, Spain

²Biomedica Molecular Medicine SL, Madrid, Spain.

³ Service of Stomatology and Maxillofacial Surgery, University General Hospital. Medicina Oral Unit, Valencia University.

⁴Genomics Unit Cantoblanco, Parque Científico de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

⁵Molecular Oncology and Pathology Lab, Hospital Universitario La Paz-IdiPAZ, Madrid, Spain

⁶Medical Oncology Department, Instituto Ramón y Cajal de Investigación Sanitaria (IRYCIS), CIBERONC, Madrid, Spain.

*Corresponding authors:

jose.v.bagan@uv.es, cristinapenamaroto@gmail.com

Postal Addresses:

Jose Vicente Bagan
Universidad de Valencia, Servicio de Estomatología y CMF, Hospital General Universitario de Valencia, 46014 Valencia, Spain

Cristina Peña
Instituto Ramón y Cajal de Investigación Sanitaria (IRYCIS)
Laboratorio de Investigación de Oncología Médica
Planta -2 Dcha
Carretera de Colmenar, km 9,100
28034 Madrid, Spain

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION:

Conceptualization: Carlos Llorens, José V. Bagan

Selection of patients and samples obtained for posterior analysis: Jose V. Bagan, Leticia Bagan

Methodology: Carlos Llorens, Ricardo Ramos-Ruiz, Beatriz Soriano, Lucia Trilla-Fuertes, Angelo Gamez-Pozo.

Data interpretation and Writing: Carlos Llorens, Cristina Peña, José V. Bagan

Writing - review and editing: Carlos Llorens, Cristina Peña, José V. Bagan

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Supervision: José V. Bagan

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The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: To explore the pathophysiology of Proliferative Verrucous Leukoplakia, a rare oral-disorder that exhibits high rates of recurrence and malignant transformation, through a RNAseq case-control study.

Material and Methods: We obtained oral biopsies from 10 patients with Verrucous Leukoplakia lesions and from the mucosa of 5 healthy individuals for sequencing using RNAseq technology. Using bioinformatic methods, we investigated gene expression and enrichment differences between patients both with and without the disorder. We applied network biology methods to investigate functional relations among those genes that were differentially deregulated.

Results: We detected 140 differentially expressed genes with distinct roles in immune surveillance, tissue and organ morphogenesis, development and organization. Of these 140 genes, 111 have been previously described as cancer expression biomarkers, being Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma the most represented type of cancer among them. Of these 140 genes, 26 were prioritized for further investigation as biomarkers using larger sample sizes.

Conclusions: The gene expression patterns of healthy and unhealthy patients differed in 140 genes whose deregulation has a functional impact on normal functioning of the immune system. This immune expression profile provides a plausible hypothesis to explain the transformation to oral squamous cell carcinoma observed in 6 of the 10 assayed cases.

Clinical Relevance: By determining the molecular bases of the Proliferative Verrucous Leukoplakia disorder and identifying early biomarkers of malignancy, this can allow us to develop new treatment strategies.

KEYWORDS:

Proliferative Verrucous Leukoplakia, Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma, Differential expression, Gene ontology, Protein-protein Interaction Networks, Immune response, Fiber Organization.

INTRODUCTION

Proliferative verrucous leukoplakia (PVL) is a rare, potentially oral, malignant disorder that was first described by Hansen et al. in 1985 [1]. Since then, only a few studies have reported on this disorder in a relevant number of patients [2, 3]. In addition, these patients were commonly non-smoking females with the gingiva primarily being the affected area [4].

According to the “2017 fourth edition of the World Health Organization Classification of Tumors of the Head and Neck” PVL starts as a simple homogeneous leukoplakia but in time can progress and extend to multiple areas of the oral cavity [5]. PVLs often develop into oral cancer and can recur after clinical treatments. Currently, there is no known etiological cause behind the development of the disease. Some years ago, several authors suggested the role of human papillomavirus on its pathogenesis [6, 7], although this is still under debate [8, 9].

Previous studies suggest that the malignant transformation of PVL is around 70% [14]. Moreover, erythroleukoplakia exhibited malignant transformation in 100% of the patients [13]. In addition, these patients may develop several primary oral cancers during the evolution of the PVL. For instance, we recently reported on 33 PVL cases that had developed ≥ 2 oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC). Furthermore, as the number of OSCCs increased, the temporal intervals between them became shorter [15].

One of the issues that has historically hindered studies on PVL is that until recently there were no effective methods for its diagnosis. To establish a uniform diagnosis, some authors proposed different diagnosis criteria for PVL [10-13].

In particular, some authors have tried to identify the biomolecular mechanisms that could help us to understand the pathogenesis of this disease. Molecular alterations in a specific genetic region such as p16INK4a and p14ARF aberrations (common in oral verrucous leukoplakia) in the locus 9p21 have been related with distinct histologic types of oral premalignancy [16]. However, there is no conclusive evidence of correlation between the prevalence of PVL and DNA aneuploidy, loss of heterozygosity at locus 9p21, or the specific expression of Mcm (mini chromosome maintenance) protein [17]. In a recent systematic review, Rintala et al. found that aneuploidy might be a valuable structural biomarker for PVL diagnosis but it should be further validated [18].

Nevertheless, there is still no clear reason to explain why some many PVL patients develop cancers and secondary primary tumors.

In the current post-genomic era, high-throughput technologies, including Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) are central to investigating the molecular biology of the diseases. NGS provides opportunities to identify novel biomarkers for pathological diagnostic, prognostic, and treatment response but also for improved characterization of the molecular mechanisms of diseases. Consequently, we used RNAseq study to investigate the molecular biology of PVL and determine why this disease presents a high rate of malignant transformation to OSCC.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Patients and sample preparation: This study is based on 15 fresh-frozen oral mucosal biopsies from a cohort of 15 participants which were distributed in two groups: the case study PVL group constituted by 10 patients with PVL and the control group composed by 5 healthy individuals. In the PVL two patients did not have dysplasia, 2 showed mild dysplasia, 4 moderate and 2 severe. The clinical profiles of all patients are shown in Table 1 and in Figure 1.

The diagnosis of PVL lesions was made following the criteria provided by Cerero-Lapiedra et al. [10]. In the PVL group, two biopsies were taken from representative areas of the lesions, ensuring that both the epithelium and the underlying connective tissue were included in the sampled area. One of the biopsies was used for routine histopathological analysis to make sure that the observed lesions meet the histopathological criteria to establish the diagnosis together with the clinical data in each patient. The other sample was used for RNAseq sequencing analysis. For the control group, samples were obtained from 5 healthy individuals by taking a biopsy of the mucosa area adjacent to the teeth. Biopsies of 0.1 mm depth and 10-15 mm width were collected using a scalpel blade (#11). The tissue was then frozen at -80 ° C until processing. PVL biopsies were all collected between 2017 and 2018. None of the 10 selected PVL cases presented histopathological signs of OSCC lesions at the time of the biopsy. However, it is worth noting with two years of the study, 6 out of the 10 cases with PVL have developed at least one OSCC and 4 of them had developed more than one (see Table 1).

RNA Library preparation and sequencing: RNA from clinical samples was extracted using the Monarch® Total RNA Miniprep kit (New England Biolabs) followed by treatment with DNase to remove any possible DNA contamination. RNA amounts and integrity profiles were determined using the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer using RNA 6000 nano LabChip kit. Libraries were prepared according to the instructions of the Kit “NEBNext Ultra Directional RNA Library Prep kit for Illumina” (New England Biolabs), following the protocol “Poly(A) mRNA Magnetic Isolation Module”. The fragmentation time used was 8-10 min, and it was adjusted slightly according to the specific RIN values. The obtained libraries were validated and quantified by an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer using a DNA7500 LabChip kit. Equimolecular pool of libraries were titrated by quantitative PCR using the “Kapa-SYBR FAST qPCR kit forLightCycler480” (Kapa BioSystems) and a reference standard of known concentration. The pool of libraries was denatured prior to being seeded on a NextSeq flowcell at a density of 2,2pM, where clusters were formed and sequenced using a “NextSeq™ 500 High Output Kit”, in a 1x75 single read sequencing run. An average of 15 million of pass-filter reads were obtained (range 13.9 – 17.0 x 10⁶), which were used for further filtering and bioinformatics analysis.

Bioinformatic analyses: Pre-processing: Quality control on Fastq libraries was performed using FastQC [19]. Subsequently, Fastq files were preprocessed using Cutadapt2.3 [20] and Prinseq-lite-020.4 [21] to eliminate primers and low-quality sequences. Mapping and differential expression analyses: Preprocessed fastq files were mapped on the human genome GRCh38.95 version provided by the Ensembl release 96 [22], using Tophat 2.1.1 [23]. The overall read mapping rates successfully ranged from 86% to 96% of reads mapped. Bam files resulted from mapping with Tophat were used as input to Cufflinks/Cuffdiff to perform a Differential Expression (DE) analysis between the PVL study group (constituted by 10 samples) and the control group (constituted by 5 samples) as described in [24]. The different samples (libraries) belonging to each group (PVL and/or control) were taken as biological replicates since they correspond to different individuals. Differentially expressed genes supported by a Benjamini-Hochberg False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction < 0.05 were considered as statistically significant. Statistical analyses were performed using CummeRbund [25].

All differentially expressed genes were provided with annotations (regarding Gene names, descriptions, Gene Ontologies (GO), Enzyme Commission Numbers (ECs), metabolic pathways) using Biomart at Ensembl [22] and the KEGG [26] knowledge database. Finally, an enrichment analysis of GOs was performed using Goseq [27] based on the results of differential expression. To perform these analyses all assayed genes were previously provided with annotations of GOs retrieved from Ensembl Biomart [22, 28]. Enriched GO terms and pathways supported by p-value corrected by $FDR < 0.05$ in the resulting Wallenius distribution, were considered as statistically significant. The above described steps for RNAseq data processing and differential expression and enrichment analysis, were executed using the Tophat-Cufflinks pipeline provided by RNAseq app of the GPRO suite [29].

Network analyses: The Fragments per Kilobase of exon model per Million reads Mapped (FPKM) reported in the DE analysis of all differentially expressed genes were used to build a Probabilistic Graphical Model (PGM) using R v.3.2.5 and gRapHD package [30] as previously described in [31]. PGMs (which are undirected acyclic graphs) are built by obtaining the spreading over the tree that maximizes the likelihood and then choosing the network graph that preserves the network decomposability and minimizes the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) with the simplest structure [32]. To also assess enrichment of Protein-Protein interactions (PPI) and other functional associations among the 140 DE genes, we used the STRING V11 web server [33] and three active interaction sources (experiments, databases, co-expression,) and a minimum required interaction score of 0.500. Functional and network relationships were also determined among the 140 genes using the GO information provided by STRING to distribute the genes into two functional groups according to their ontologies and neighboring relationship in the network structure

Data availability: Raw data have been deposited at the NCBI SRA archive with BioProject record PRJNA592439, and BioSample records (SAMN13426702, SAMN13426703, SAMN13426704, SAMN13426705, SAMN13426706, SAMN13426707, SAMN13426708, SAMN13426709, SAMN13426710, SAMN13426711, SAMN13426712, SAMN13426713, SAMN13426714, SAMN13426715, SAMN13426716).

Ethics statement: This study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Human Research of the University of Valencia (Ref. H1523722754549). Informed written consent was obtained from all participants after an explanation of the nature of the study.

RESULTS

Clinical samples and gene expression of PVL patients and healthy individuals.

All RNAseq samples were sequenced by Illumina Technology and used to perform a differential expression (DE) analysis between the PVL and control group. The DE analysis reported 140 genes as deregulated under False Discovery Rate (FDR) < 0.05 (Figure 2A). Out of these 140 genes, 100 were up-regulated and 40 down-regulated in the PVL group respect to the control group. A full summary of the DE results for these 140 genes is provided in Supplementary Material 1. As shown in Figures 2B and 2C, the dispersion (inter-library variation between replicates) and the median of the expression values were similar in both groups thus supporting the viability of the comparison of both groups in a DE analysis. Figure 2D reveals a reasonable individual over-dispersion among samples due to their intrinsic variability. Notice that the samples showed good separation by the pathological condition in this analysis (component M2 in Figure 2D) revealing some biological variation differences (and therefore some DE differences to exist among the PVL and the controls samples, excepting Control-4 which showed higher intrinsic variation than other control samples. Control-4 is a healthy individual whose deviation respect to other controls would be due to many reasons (genetics, epigenetics environmental). We kept Control-4 in the study as the DE test was performed between groups thus meaning that any possible bias provided by Control-4 to the study was corrected by the other control samples since we used 5 replicates to constitute that group.

Gene Ontology enrichment analysis at the whole transcriptome level between the PVL and the control groups

We investigated functional differences in gene expression, as determined by differential enrichment of Gene Ontology (GO) categories, by performing a GOfseq comparison at the whole transcriptome level. This analysis identified statistically significant increases in the expression of 44 GOs (Supplementary Material 2). Six of the 44 enriched GOs

correspond to Cellular Components (CC) related to different sub-localizations such as the extracellular space plasma membrane, complement component C1 complex, and immunological synapse. This latter feature in particular indicates the predominance of transcripts for secreted proteins as well as interfaces for antigen-presenting cells. Another 26 of the 44 enriched GOs corresponded to Biological Processes (BP) that were mainly related to immune system processes as well as chemotaxis, release of sequestered calcium ion, cell motility and adhesion, morphogenesis, formation and differentiation homeostasis and positive regulation of transcription. The remainder of the GO enrichment observed in the PVL group pertained to 12 GOs for Molecular Functions (MF) including genes encoding for transcription factors and proteins with binding functions especially for actin and cytoskeletal binding.

Cancer biomarkers within the set of genes shown as deregulated in the PVL group

Literature searches performed in the PubMed Central database at NCBI [34] revealed that the set of 140 deregulated genes in the PVL group were particularly enriched in cancer expression biomarkers. As shown in Table 2, at least 111 of these 140 genes have been previously described as deregulated in studies focused on cancer expression. Moreover, 35 of them are reported as OSCC expression biomarkers. The status of deregulation (“up” or “down”) that we report here is consistent with what has been previously reported for 91 of those 111 genes that have been previously related with cancer expression (Supplementary Material 1). All this evidence suggests that these 140 DE are characteristic of the PVL pathology. The biological functional processes derived from these DE genes could also act as the precursors for the development of OSCC.

Functional aspects related with the Pathophysiology of the PVL group based on the roles and network interactions of the deregulated genes

Downstream analyses performed with the STRING server to evaluate the functional profiles specifically associated to the set of 140 DE genes revealed significant enrichment of GOs regarding 172 BPs and 5 CCs (Supplementary Material 2). Most of these GOs were already reported as differentially enriched by the Goseq analysis between the PVL and the control groups at the whole transcriptome level (Supplementary Material 2). This indicates that the major source of variation in gene expression derives from the deregulation of these 140 genes. Besides, the STRING

server also revealed more functional interactions than expected by random events among these 140 genes (p-value < 1e-16 in STRING server). These 140 DE genes can be networked according to their expression patterns without other a priori information using probabilistic graphical models (PGM) and Protein-Protein interactions (PPI) and separated into two major functional groups (Figure 3). One of these groups, collects 58 of the 140 DE genes and has been labeled as “Activation and regulation of the immune response” since 30 of these 58 DE genes present GOs related with the immunity (nodes highlighted with red dots). The other group collects the remaining 82 DE genes. While 12 of these 82 are related with immunity, the enrichment of GOs in this group is more properly related with processes related with “Morphogenesis, development and organization of muscle cells, tissues and organs” as identified by the STRING server.

The group for “activation and regulation of the immune response” is significantly enriched in GOs for BPs related with the activation and positive regulation of immune system, the inflammatory and the defense responses. They are also associated with other BPs such as secretion, cell adhesion, signaling regulation, leukocyte migration and motility. As for CCs, this group is enriched in GOs relating to sub-localizations such as immunological synapse, plasma membrane complement component C1 complex, and extracellular region. As for MFs, the enrichment shows predominance of GOs corresponding to protein binding (remarkably cytokine and signaling receptor binding functions), as well as for activities such as dimerization and glutathione peroxidase (Supplementary Material 2). Thus, the immunological profile of the 58 DE genes suggests that the deregulation observed in the PVL group is related to the alteration of binding proteins and receptors. These proteins and receptors are involved in the modulation of the innate and adaptive immune responses, key processes across distinct cellular sub-localizations including interfaces between antigen-presenting cells and lymphocytes, salivary secretome and the classical complement pathway. A major PPI network (pink nodes) detected within this group reveals a wide number of functional interactions among the products of the 18 DE genes. Thus, we have highlighted these genes as potential candidates for further validation as biomarkers for PVL diagnosis and potential targets for immunotherapeutic approaches. In this PPI network, *LCK*, *CD5*, *CD6*, *IKZF3* and *PTPN7* play a role in the selection, differentiation, maturation and proliferation of developing T-cells; *FYB* and *CARD11* are involved in signaling cascades in T-cells; *STAT4*, *EPHB2*, *CCL5*, *CCL19*, *CXCR3*, *CCR7* and *ILRG* are

involved in cellular signal transduction; *CD8A* play a role in the response to both external and internal insults; and *C2*, *CIQA* and *CIQB* are major members of the serum complement system. Another PPI network that we would like to highlight for further potential biomarker validations is the one constituted by the three genes in which their protein products, namely *GBP1*, *GBP5* and *IFI44L*, play a role in the cellular defense against external insults.

The second group of DE genes is enriched in GO categories corresponding to BPs related to “morphogenesis, development and organization in muscle cells, tissues and organs”. This group encompasses processes for actin filament and fiber organization, assembly and sliding, as well as actin-mediated cell contraction and actomyosin structure organization. This group is also enriched in BPs related to regulation of gene expression, cellular and organismal processes, and ganglioside biosynthetic processes. Regarding the CCs in this second group, we found a significant enrichment in GOs categories related to both ‘contractile fiber part’ and ‘neurofibrillary tangle’ sub-localizations (Supplementary Material 2). In this regard, two PPI networks (denoted in blue nodes) highlight that 8 DE genes in this second group would also be interesting candidates for further assessments as potential biomarkers. One of these PPI networks is constituted by genes encoding for the TTN, ACTC1, SCIN and TPM1 proteins which are known to play different roles in actin fiber organization, assembly of muscle cells, cell motility and exocytosis. The other network involves genes encoding for the PROC, BPIF2, TMEM182A and TNC proteins which are known to play a role in blood coagulation, innate immunity, cell death resistance, synaptic plasticity and neuronal regeneration, among others.

DISCUSSION

In this study we performed a differential gene expression analysis between patients with and without PVL lesions, in an aim to investigate and characterize the molecular signatures associated with this pathology. Our analysis showed that differentially expressed genes in PLV patients, compared to healthy controls, are enriched in biological process related to modulation of immune surveillance as well as tissue and organ morphogenesis. Two previous RNAseq studies concerning similar pathologies have been reported in the literature. In particular, Zhang *et al.* [35] studied oral dysplasias and Farah and Fox [36] analyzed a cohort of 24 patients with leukoplakia

with and without dysplasia. However, our study is the first to describe the transcriptomic profile of the PVL pathology.

A plausible hypothesis to explain the immune response in the PVL patients could be microbiological infection. Different studies, including also our data investigated the link between PVL and HPV, but all of them showed inconclusive results [9]. Thus, the HPV infection analysis was out of the scope of the present study and was not assessed. In addition, we did not identify an etiologic agent to convincingly explain the pathogenesis of this disease. On the other hand, PVL disorders are quite resistant to therapeutic approaches (including antimicrobial prescription) presenting high recurrence and a high rate of oral cancer evolution [37]. Consequently, it could also be hypothesized that these PVL lesions modify the immunosurveillance as one of the first steps of tumor initiation. Our study supports this hypothesis but to provide unequivocal proof would require studies with larger sample sizes and including those with tumors. The knowledge of how PVL regulates immunosurveillance provided the opportunity to develop new therapies based on immunotherapeutic approaches. Supporting this idea, Bailiang *et al.* recently described different immune subtypes in squamous cell carcinoma providing a conceptual framework of immune modulation in these tumors, which might contribute to the design of treatment strategies and patient selection for immunotherapy [38]. In the other hand, the involvement of tumor microenvironment, including connective tissue and different stromal cells, is an important factors of tissue functionality. Therefore, our RNAseq study performed in the whole tissue, with epithelial cells, underlying connective tissue and stromal cells, directly impact our results and could be considered as a limitation of our study. Even though this would require better characterization, due to the scarce and necessary data about PVL the aim of our study was to describe the “snapshot” of this disease, including all of the cell players at the transcriptomic level. Therefore, we developed a pilot study including PVL and normal oral mucosa samples to determine deregulated genes in PVL lesion. Interestingly, our analyses have shown many deregulated genes related with immune surveillance which may be considered as a biomarker of PVL or even as a potential cancer progression biomarker, independently of the type of cell is which they are expressed.

No samples used in this study presented tumoral characteristics upon extraction. After two years however, six samples had evolved into oral cancer. This highlights the importance of finding molecular biomarkers for the appearance of OSCC derived from

PLV. As the early detection of OSCC reduces mortality and morbidity, there is a need to improve the classification of risk oral cancer patients, including those with potentially malignant disorders. Due to recent advances in high-throughput technologies, including next-generation RNA sequencing, new approaches have enabled us to identify novel biomarkers for pathological diagnostic, prognostics, treatment response, and patients monitoring. Our study shows specific enrichment in biological process related to tissue and organ morphogenesis development, and organization in PVL patients. It is largely known that tumor cells progress to pathologically advanced stages by altering their shape and interacting with both other cells and the extracellular matrix to inflict tissue disruption evolving in local invasion and distant metastasis [39]. Thus, the recognition of these biological processes related to cell morphology, locomotion and motility could be used as a first indicator of tumor initiation.

Interestingly, the resulting network from the PGM analysis showed many deregulated genes involved in the two major functional groups that were either related to the development of OSCC or described as biomarkers of tumor transformation. The specific interaction among the different genes of the network is discussed in Supplementary Material 3. The high number of deregulated genes in PVLs supports the idea that PVL lesions represent a significant pre-cancer niche for malignant transformation and thus, initiation of OSCC development.

PVL is an oral disorder that frequently evolves to carcinoma despite treatment and intervention. Moreover, PVL tends to develop several second primary tumors in the same patient, further threatening the survival of these patients. Even though the confirmation of malignant transformation should be addressed via histopathology confirmation, the accumulation of genetic and epigenetic alterations is nowadays thought to be main source of carcinogenesis [40]. Thus, determining the molecular basis of this disorder and identifying early biomarkers of malignancy would allow us to develop new strategies for treatment.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

Conflict of Interest: All authors, Carlos Llorens, Beatriz Soriano, Lucia Trilla-Fuertes, Leticia Bagan, Ricardo Ramos-Ruiz, Angelo Gamez-Pozo, Cristina Peña, and Jose V. Bagan, declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Ethical approval: All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. This study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Human Research of the University of Valencia (Ref. H1523722754549).

Informed consent: Informed written consent was obtained from all participants after an explanation of the nature of the study, as approved by the Ethics Committee for Human Research of the University of Valencia.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1.- Multiple PVL areas affecting the oral mucosa: A) Soft palate; B) Tongue and alveolar ridge; C) Clinical follow up of a patient showing appearance of OSCC in the lower right alveolar ridge.

Figure 2.- One-hundred differential genes were deregulated between PVL and control groups: A) Volcano plot representing the log₂ adjusted p-values against the Log₂ Fold Change expression values obtained in the differential expression analysis. Red dots highlight the 140 DE genes reported as deregulated under an FDR < 0.05. B) Dispersion plot representing the deviation from the threshold in the sequencing libraries used in each group against the Counts of Fragments Per Kilobase of transcript per Million mapped reads (FPKM). C) Box plot of the expression of the FPKM per group in log₁₀ scale. D) Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) plot showing the clustering relationships and sources of variability of the libraries of the control and PVL groups.

Figure 3.- Functional network showing two major functional groups of genes involved in the modulation of immune surveillance as well as in tissue and organ morphogenesis, development and organization. Nodes represent the DE genes. The correspondent protein or ncRNA names are shown. Genes highlighted with red dots correspond to those involved in immune system dynamics. Dashed links define the edges of the most likely network structure interconnecting the 140 DE genes according to their expression profiles as inferred by Probabilistic Graphical Model (PGM) methods (see Materials and methods for further description). The rest of the links correspond to 9 PPI networks identified by the STRING server among 39 of the 140

genes, using a minimum required interaction score of 0.500 and 3 active interaction sources (experiments, databases, co-expression). The links of the PPI networks as well as the correspondent nodes are colored as represented by default by the STRING server as follows: the major PPI network is constituted by 18 genes colored pink; the 2 PPI networks of 4 genes each were colored blue; the PPI network of 3 genes was colored in yellow; the 5 PPIs between the 2 genes were colored in green. Lastly, the 140 DE genes were distributed into two functional groups according to their neighboring relationships and their ontologies as provided by the STRING server (see Materials and methods for further details).

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary Material 1.- Deregulated genes. 1) Tab “DE genes”: Summary of the DE analysis results for the 140 genes found to be deregulated in the comparison between tPVL and control patients at FDR q-value < 0.05. 2) Tab “cancer biomarkers”: Literature search on the 140 DE genes and their relationship as expression biomarkers in different types of cancers including OSCC, accompanied by a comparative analysis of the status of de-regulation of each gene as described in the literature and as reported in this study.

Supplementary Material 2.- Enrichments. 1) Tab “Whole transcriptome level”: GO categories reported as significant by GO enrichment analysis using Goseq and the Wallenius distribution. 2) Tab “Network Scenario”: GO enrichment values for the 140 deregulated genes constituting the network scenario shown in Figure 3. 3) Tabs “Immune response” and “morphogenesis and development”: functional GO enrichment values with p-value < 0.05 as observed in the STRING enrichment analyses performed on the genes assigned to each group.

Supplementary Material 3.- Extended discussion and literature cited for the specific interactions among the different genes shown in the network displayed in Figure 3.